

RURAL-URBAN INFLUX: RETHINKING THE IMPLICATIONS AND CHALLENGES FOR URBAN ADMINISTRATION IN ENUGU STATE NIGERIA

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Keywords: Rural–Urban Influx, Urban Change, Sustainable Urban Planning, Population Growth, Enugu State.	Abstract: Rural–urban influx has remained one of the most significant drivers of urban change in developing countries, especially Nigeria with wide-range of implications for population growth, settlement patterns, and the adequacy of public infrastructure. In Nigeria, and particularly in Enugu State, the phenomenon has intensified in recent years, raising concerns about sustainable urban planning and management. This study therefore examined Rural-Urban Influx: Rethinking the implications and challenges for urban administration in Enugu State Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted, and data were elicited from respondents using questionnaire, in-depth interview, observation and focus group discussion guide. The major findings indicates that rural –urban influx has significantly increased insecurity, pollution and housing crises in Enugu State, especially the metropolis. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the Enugu State Government should establish a strong security outfit to contend with the rising incidences of insecurity in the State. Also, low housing settlements should be built by the Government to settle the low income earners who migrated from the rural communities.
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1. Introduction

Rural-urban influx is synonymous to rural-urban migration. This social malady has become one of the most teething problems. It has undoubtedly posed myriad of challenges to urban administration in Nigeria. Rural-urban influx can also be described as a process where individuals and households move from rural areas to urban centers in search of better economic opportunities, access to education, healthcare, and improved living conditions. In Nigeria, this trend has accelerated due to rural poverty, agricultural decline, insecurity, and increasing urbanization pressures (Chukwuemeka, Nebo and Okechukwu, 2013). This internal migration has significantly contributed to the rapid expansion of urban centers in Nigeria, often surpassing the capacity of planning institutions and urban management frameworks (Chukwuemeka, Nebo and Okechukwu 2013). As rural dwellers move to urban areas in search of better livelihoods, employment opportunities, and access to services, cities face mounting pressure to accommodate this influx; a process often marred by poor planning, resource shortages, and weak policy implementation.

In Enugu State, especially Metropolitan cities, urban administration appears to be difficult due to high influx of people who have migrated from the rural communities in search of greener

pasture. The strain on public infrastructure and services in Enugu Metropolis has become increasingly evident. Public schools and healthcare facilities are overstretched, waste management is inadequate, and traffic congestion is worsening. With an already limited urban budget, local planning authorities struggle to expand infrastructure at the pace required by the growing population. According to Ezenekwe and Eze (2021), the disjointed relationship between population growth and infrastructural investment in Anambra's urban areas contributes significantly to service inefficiencies and public health risks.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Rural-urban influx popularly known as rural-urban migration in Nigeria and Enugu State in particular has posed myriad of challenges. The underlying challenges and imbroglio have created big gap and frustrated the desired development in Enugu State. It has also created serious challenges to urban administration too. A cursory look at the incidences of crime, cultism among youths and other social vices leaves nothing to be desired. Rural –Urban influx has implications for the rural communities and urban centers. Some of the implications for the rural areas range from declining productivity, poverty, and food insecurity and labor shortages. Also, the urban centers have more serious consequences of this 19th century phenomenon.

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However, it is pertinent to interrogate some of the aforementioned variables. Without doubt, this social malady has posed serious challenges especially in Enugu Metropolitan centers. They include strained infrastructures, overcrowding, increased unemployment, rise in pollution, informal settlement, insecurity, access to basic social services and housing crises.

Thus, this study is determined to carry and in-depth analysis of some of the underlying problems, which include insecurity, rise in pollution and housing crises.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- 1) To determine the extent rural-influx has heightened insecurity in Enugu State
- 2) To examine the influence of rural-urban influx on urban pollution, especially in Enugu State
- 3) To investigate the extent rural-urban influx has increased housing crises in Enugu State.

1.3 Hypotheses

- 1) High rate of insecurity in Enugu State has nexus with rural-urban influx
- 2) Urban pollution has worsened in Enugu State due to rural-urban influx
- 3) Rural-urban influx has increased housing crises in Enugu State

1.4 Scope of the Study

The study was anchored on Enugu State, and specifically Enugu metropolis was the stress point. The timing of the study was 2010=20225.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Underpinning

2.1.1 Rural-Urban Influx

Rural–urban influx in order words known as migration has been widely recognized as one of the most significant demographic phenomena shaping the development of cities in developing countries. It is generally defined as the movement of people from rural areas, which are often characterized by low population density, agricultural livelihoods, and limited infrastructure, to urban centers where opportunities for wage employment, education, and social services are perceived to be greater (Oyeleye, 2023). According to Chukwuemeka and Umeifekwem (2024), rural–urban migration is largely motivated by the desire of individuals to improve their economic conditions, access modern amenities, and secure better standards of living. Similarly, (Chukwuemeka and Chukwujindu, 2013) in his push–pull framework explains that migration results from the interaction of repelling factors in rural areas, such as poverty, unemployment, and poor services and attractive conditions in urban centers like jobs, infrastructure, and social mobility. This makes migration not only a demographic shift but also a reflection of wider socio-economic imbalances between rural and urban regions.

The theoretical underpinnings of rural–urban migration have been explained from different perspectives. For instance, Lewis (2024) argues that migration is driven by the existence of

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surplus labor in the agricultural (rural) sector which is absorbed into the modern industrial (urban) sector, thereby facilitating economic transformation. Building on this, the Chukwuemeka and umeifekwem (2024) emphasize that people migrate not just because of actual wage differentials but because of expected income, even when urban unemployment is high. In contrast, Stark and Bloom, (2021) shift the focus from the individual to the household, highlighting that migration is often a family strategy to diversify income and minimize risks arising from credit and insurance market failures in rural settings. These theoretical perspectives converge on the view that migration is not random but a rational response to opportunities and constraints shaped by economic, social, and institutional structures. Empirical evidence also reveals the multiple drivers of rural–urban migration.

2.1.2 Urban Planning

Urban planning is the professional practice of developing and managing land use and the built environment to create thriving sustainable and equitable communities. It involves a technical and political process that uses knowledge from various fields like engineering, economics, and sociology to shape the future of cities and towns addressing aspects such as land use, infrastructure, housing, transportation, and environmental concerns (Chukwuemeka, Ewuim, Okolo, Umeifekwem, 2013).

The concept of urban planning has evolved significantly over time. Traditional planning approaches emphasized rigid master plans that sought to control land use and settlement patterns through zoning and regulation. However, these approaches often failed in rapidly urbanizing contexts of the Global South, where migration and informality outpaced the capacity of institutions to enforce plans (Watson, 2019). More contemporary approaches advocate **strategic and participatory planning**, which emphasizes flexibility, stakeholder inclusion, and the integration of informal settlements into formal urban frameworks (Wilson, et al, 2023; UN-Habitat, 2020). **Angel et al. (2016)** argue that modern planning must anticipate inevitable urban expansion by securing adequate land for infrastructure and housing rather than reacting belatedly to unregulated growth.

Urban governance and planning constraints further exacerbate the issue. Weak institutional frameworks, inadequate enforcement of land-use policies, and limited investment in affordable housing encourage the proliferation of informal settlements. According to **Cookey and Ochuba (2024)**, the combination of rapid migration, poor urban planning, and economic constraints often results in settlements that are physically and socially marginalized, making them difficult to integrate into the formal city structure. Similarly, **Wilson,**

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Nwankwo, and George (2023) note that informal settlements often occupy environmentally vulnerable areas such as floodplains or steep slopes, increasing residents' exposure to hazards and limiting the potential for infrastructural development.

The **social and economic implications** of informal settlements are multifaceted. On one hand, they provide immediate and affordable housing for low-income urban populations, supporting urban labor markets and informal economic activities. On the other hand, they pose significant challenges for urban planners and policymakers. Informal settlements are often overcrowded, lacking essential services such as clean water, sanitation, waste management, and electricity, which can lead to public health risks, environmental degradation, and social inequities (**Essien, 2024; UN-Habitat, 2020**). Their rapid, unregulated growth complicates municipal service delivery, infrastructure expansion, and long-term urban planning efforts.

The literature also highlights the **dynamic nature of informal settlements**. They are not static; over time, they may evolve into more formalized neighborhoods through government intervention, community organization, and incremental upgrading. However, in the absence of proactive planning and policy support, these settlements often remain marginalized, perpetuating cycles of poverty and

infrastructural deficits (Akuabata and Chukwuemeka, 2023). Looking at Enugu State informal settlements are closely tied to rural–urban migration. The influx of migrants has increased the demand for affordable housing and contributed to unplanned urban expansion, highlighting the critical intersection between population movement, urban planning, and service delivery. Addressing informal settlements requires integrated urban planning strategies that combine land regularization, affordable housing provision, infrastructure development, and inclusive governance to ensure **sustainable urban growth**.

2.1.5 Insecurity and Crime

Urbanization is linked to increased insecurity through drivers like rural-urban influx driven by rural insecurity and conflict, and the creation of urban poverty and food insecurity, housing crises due to economic pressures, poor governance, and rapid unplanned growth that overwhelms existing infrastructure and services. Conversely, insecurity such as conflict, can fuel more migration to cities, exacerbating these urban challenges and creating a cycle where each exacerbates the other (Nebo, Chukwuemeka, Okechukwu, 2013).

How Insecurity Drives Urbanization

Insecurity in rural areas often stemming from conflict, lack of justice, unemployment, or ethnic crises – forces people to migrate to urban centers in search of safety and better life.

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Environmental degradation like the Niger Delta environmental degradation caused by resource exploitation can make rural livelihoods impossible, further pushing people to the cities. Also urbanization contributes to insecurity through the massive inflow of migrants to cities, often low skill and low-wage workers, strains urban resources and can lead to an increase in urban poverty, particularly for those dependent on purchased food (Chukwuemeka, 2013)

According to Newman (2018), urban crime can be broadly defined as “any criminal act that is facilitated by the concentration of people, resources, and opportunities in an urban environment.” Similarly, Otu (2019) notes that urban crime reflects the intersection of social disorganization, unemployment, and rapid urbanization, often leading to offenses such as theft, assault, burglary, and organized violence. Scholars have conceptualized urban crime through different lenses. The social disorganization perspective, as advanced by Shaw and McKay (2022) and revisited in modern urban criminology, views urban crime as arising from weakened community bonds and inadequate social institutions in fast-growing cities. More recent studies such as Oyeleke (2020) argue that rapid migration into cities without corresponding infrastructural and economic expansion creates an “urban underclass” that becomes vulnerable to criminal

activities. In this sense, crime becomes both a survival strategy and a response to inequality.

From another angle, Adepoju (2017) describes urban crime as a by-product of “structural strain” where individuals are unable to achieve societal goals through legitimate means, thereby resorting to illegal alternatives. This interpretation links urban crime directly with socio-economic pressures such as poverty, unemployment, and housing shortages, which are common features of urban centers in developing countries. In the Nigerian context, urban crime is closely associated with the challenges of rapid urbanization. Umeadi and Chukwu (2021) emphasize that the growth of informal settlements, poor urban planning, and overstretched public services contribute to an environment where crime thrives. They further argue that cities like Lagos, Abuja, and Awka experience rising levels of urban insecurity due to the mismatch between population growth and urban governance capacity. Conceptually, therefore, urban crime can be seen as both a symptom of structural imbalance in urban areas and a challenge to sustainable urban development (Osita-Njoku & Chikere, 2025)

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. This method was considered because it gives the researcher the opportunity to sample

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the opinion of people and obtain current information from the respondents.

3.2 Method of data Collection

The main instrument of the data collection that used in this study is a structured questionnaire. The designed questionnaire was divided into two sections. The questions in section A is the general information while section B is meant to directly address the research question.

3.3 Population of the Study

According to Chukwuemeka (2019) population is animate and inanimate things. There, the population of the study that was randomly selected comprises stakeholders from five local government in Enugu State. The Local

Table 3.1: Distribution of Respondents

S/N	LGA	Number of respondents
1	Enugu North	85
2	Enugu East	95
3	Enugu South	80
4	Nsukka	65
5	Nkanu West	75
	Total	400

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The researcher used convenience sampling technique. The choice for the convenience sampling technique is anchor on the ease to reach potential respondents at the geopolitical zones mentioned.

government selected were those that have urban status. They are Enugu North, Enugu South, Enugu East, Nsukka and Nkanu West. Thus, the total stakeholders randomly selected was 400 as per the distribution table below.

3.4 Sample and Sampling Technique

Due to the largeness of the population size, the study randomly selected respondents from each of the local governments selected in the Enugu State. This makes the total sample size for the study to be 400. The essence of this is to have sample size that can be handled efficiently by the researcher and also to ensure that each state was portioned same figure with every state under study.

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques

. Measure of central tendency was adopted to measure the spread of the datasets using the standard deviation. Furthermore, inferential statistics such as regression analysis were used in this study. Linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses.

Decision Rule: The p-value was set at 0.05. If the p value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected; otherwise, it was accepted.

4. Data Analysis

4.1 Presentation of Data

Table 4.1.1: Questionnaire Distribution and Return

Questionnaire	Respondents	Percentage of Respondents (%)
Returned	325	81.3
Not returned	75	18.7
Total distributed	400	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The copies of questionnaire administered were 400 and 325 (81.3%) of it were returned, while 75(18.7%) were not returned. The 325 copies of questionnaires that were returned are

Table 4.1.2: Distribution of Respondents According to Sex

OPTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Male	189	58.2
Female	136	41.8
Total	325	100

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

The above table 4.1.2 shows the gender of the respondents. In the table, 189 respondents representing 58.2% of the entire respondents are

This chapter presents the analysis of the research data and interpretation of results. In analyzing the data from the questionnaires administered, simple percentage was used by the researcher, test statistics such as sample linear regression was used to test the hypotheses. Thus, the data collected were presented as follows:

considered large and capable enough to make valid deductions and conclusions. Hence, the research analysis was based on the returned copies of questionnaire.

males while the remaining 136 respondents representing 41.8% are females. Hence, the majority of the respondents are females. This is well illustrated in the chart below:

Table 4.1.4: Distribution of Respondents based on Educational Qualifications

OPTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
SSCE	108	33.5
B.Sc/HND	129	39.7
MA/M.Sc	72	22.2
PhD	16	4.9
Total	325	100%

(Source: Field Survey, 2025).

The above table 4.1.4 shows the distribution of the respondents based on their educational qualifications. In the table, 108 respondents representing 33.5% indicated that they were in possession of SSCE, 129 respondents representing 39.7% indicated that they have B.Sc/HND qualifications, 72 respondents

representing 22.2% indicated that they were in possession of MA/M.Sc qualifications, while the remaining 16 respondents representing 4.9% indicated he has PhD qualification. Thus, the majority of the respondents are in possession of B.Sc/HND. The bar chart illustration is shown below to give the pictorial evidence of the result:

Table 4.1.5: Descriptive statistics to analyse urban – influx and high rate of insecurity in Enugu State

S	Items	Mean	Std.Deviation
1	The Enugu State government neglected the has formulated polity to control urural urban influx	3.53	1.133
2	Enugu government has neglected insecurity and rura;-urban influx	3.42	1.003
3	Enugu state government has not considered pollution as an issue resulting from rural-urban influx	3.16	1.124
4	Enugu state government has not considered unemployment as an issue caused by rural-urban influx	2.88	1.099
5	Enugu state government has not considered poverty as a problem arising from rural-urban influx	2.72	1.109
	Average Mean	3.14	1.094

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

The results presented in table 4.1.5 revealed that respondents agreed that pollution, poverty, unemployment, housing crises and insecurity has nexus with rural-urban influx (Average Mean=3.14, Std=1.094). This was attributed to the fact that majority of the respondents agreed that Enugu state government has neglected the insecurity arising from rural-urban influx

(Mean, 3.53, Std=1.133); the state government has not been able to train the youth in skills (Mean=3.42, Std=1.003), rural urban influx contributed to the high rate of unemployed and unskilled youth in the state (Mean=3.16, Std=1.124), unemployment has driven many youths into various activities that constitute a threat to the South East states' security

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(Mean=2.88, Std=1.099) and there is strong relationship between pollution and rural –urban influx (Mean=3.14, Std=1.094). Therefore, the

above results imply rural-urban influx has nexus with high rate of insecurity in Enugu Metropolis.

Table 4.1.6: Descriptive statistics on how rural –urban influx influences pollution in Enugu State

S N	Items	Mea n	Std.Deviatio n
1	Population explosion of Enugu metropolis increases pollution	3.99	0.922
2	Juvenile delinquency resulting from rural-urban influx influence pollution	3.96	1.024
3	Low education of those who migrated from the rural communities to Enugu Metropolis increases pollution	3.85	1.067
4	Overcrowding increases urban pollution	3.81	1.028
5	High rural population in Enugu Metropolis increases open defecation	3.24	1.135
	Average Mean	3.77	1.036

(Source: Field Survey, 2025).

The results presented in table 4.1.6 revealed that respondents agreed that population explosion increases pollution in Enugu metropolis. (Average Mean=3.77, Std=1.036). This was attributed to the fact that majority of the respondents agreed that over population in Enugu metropolis increases pollution (Mean, 3.99, Std=0.922); Low level of education of those who migrated from the rural areas to Enugu

metropolis increases pollution (Mean=3.96, Std=1.026), Crowd in Enugu Metropolis has nexus with pollution|| (Mean=3.81, Std=1.028) and over population in Enugu metropolis increased the prevalence of open defecation (Mean=3.24, Std=1.135). Therefore, the above results imply that rural=urban influx has strong nexus with pollution in Enugu State , especially the metropolis

Table 4.1.7: Descriptive statistics on whether rural-urban influx has increased housing crises in Enugu State, especially Enugu State metropolis

S N	Items	Mea n	Std.Deviatio n
1	Housing crises in Enugu State, especially the metropolis is one of the consequences of rural-urban influx	3.68	.813
2	Souring cost of house rent is one of the consequences of rural-urban influx in Enugu State	3.66	.853
3	Shanty settlement is one of the problems of rural-urban influx in Enugu State	3.64	.792
4	Quit notices and tenancy case in court with landlords is one of the consequences of rural – urban influx	3.48	.843
5	Conflict between landlords and tenants in Enugu metropolis is one of the consequences of rural-urban influx	3.44	.983
	Average Mean	3.58	0.857

(Source: Field Survey, 2025).

The results presented in table 4.1.8 revealed that housing problems in Enugu metropolis is one of the problems created by rural –urban influx (average mean=3.58, Std=0.857). This was attributed to the fact that majority of the respondents agreed that the houses available could not take everybody in Enugu city. (Mean=3.68, Std=0.813), youth who lacks technical capabilities are unemployable (Mean=3.66, Std=0.853). In addition, majority of the respondents agreed that shanty settlements, high case of quit notices and conflict between landlords and tenants in Enugu

metropolis is as a result of over population in Enugu Metropolis (Mean=3.64, Std=0.792). Furthermore, some respondents agreed that the most people who migrated from rural to urban are stubborn and oftentimes may not have money to pay their rents. (Mean=3.48, Std=0.843). In the same vein, respondents agreed that frequent conflict between landlords and tenants in Enugu metropolis is as a result of high population resulting from rural-urban influx (Mean=3.44, Std=0.983). Hence, the above results imply that rural –urban influx has created a lot or problem in housing crises in Enugu State

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4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

High rate of insecurity in Enugu State has nexus with rural-urban influx

Table 4.3.1:

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.656 ^a	.431	.424	.41126	.431	68.798	1	91	.000
Model			Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.		
1	Regression		11.636	1	11.636	68.798	.000 ^b		
	Residual		15.391	323	.169				
	Total		27.027	324					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.		
	B	Std. Error		Beta					
1	(Constant)	1.495	.248			6.023	.000		
	Human capacity building	.540	.065	.656		8.294	.000		

a. Dependent variable: Insecurity
 Table 4.3.1 revealed that insecurity has nexus with rural-urban influx in Enugu State, especially the metropolis by a variance of 43.1% ($R^2=0.431$, $p=0.000$). This rejects the null hypothesis that high rate of insecurity has not nexus with rural-urban influx in Enugu state.

and upholds the alternative hypothesis. Therefore alternative/research hypothesis is accepted ($F=68.798$, $p=0.000$). **Test of Hypothesis Two**

Urban pollution has worsened in Enugu State, especially the metropolis due to rural-urban influx

Table 4.3.2:

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.674 ^a	.455	.449	.40249	.455	75.838	1	91	.000
Model			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.		
1	Regression		12.286	1	12.286	75.838	.000 ^b		
	Residual		14.742	323	.162				
	Total			324					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.		
	B	Std. Error		Beta					
1	(Constant)	1.504	.236			6.379	.000		
	Lack of youth skill training	.508	.058	.674		8.709	.000		

a. Dependent variable: Insecurity

Table 4.3.2 revealed that urban population heightens pollution metropolis of Enugu State by a variance of 45.5% ($R^2=0.455$, $p=0.000$). This rejects the null hypothesis that urban pollution has not worsened in Enugu State as a result of rural-urban influx. This therefore implies that urban pollution has worsened in Enugu State.

especially the metropolis because of rural – urban influx ($F=75.838$, $p=0.000$). Therefore we accept the research hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Rural-urban influx has increased housing crises in Enugu State

Table 4.3.3: Inadequate development of technical capabilities heighten insecurity in South East Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change

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		e	ange						
1		.345 ^a	.339	.104	.44086	.339	102.114 1 81 .000		
Model		SumofSquares		Df		MeanSquare		F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.742		1		1.581		8.132	.000 ^b
	Residual	35.179		323		.194			
	Total	39.921		324					
Model		UnstandardizedCoefficients		StandardizedCoefficients					
		B	Std.Error	Beta		T		Sig.	
1	(Constant)	3.403	.265			12.859		.000	
	Development of technical capabilities	.258	.056	.340		4.589		.000	

a. Dependent variable: Insecurity

Table 4.3.3 revealed that rural urban influx has increased housing crises in Enugu State, especially the metropolis by a variance of 33.9% ($R^2=0.339$, $p=0.000$). This rejects the null hypothesis that rural –urban influx did not increase housing crises in Enugu State, especially the metropolis. This therefore implies that rural urban influx has significantly heightens housing crises in Enugu State especially the metropolis. Furthermore, the study found that the regression model was the best fit for predicting the effect of rural urban influx and housing crises ($F=102.114$, $p=0.000$). Similarly, the study revealed that

housing crises currently experienced in Enugu State has effect on urban housing by 64.4% ($Beta=0.340$, $p=0.000$).

5. Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

1.1 Summary of Findings

1. There is a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between rural–urban influx high rate of insecurity in Enugu State.
2. There is also a very strong positive and significant relationship between pollution and urban population caused by rural-urban influx in Enugu State.

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3. The study revealed that rural-urban influx has increased housing crises in Enugu State, especially in the metropolis.

1.2 Conclusion

The study concludes that rural–urban influx has significantly shaped the urban landscape Enugu State contributing to increased crime rates, the proliferation of informal settlements, and mounting pressure on public infrastructural services. These findings reflect the broader realities of Nigerian cities, where rural–urban influx is both an opportunity for development and a challenge for sustainable urban planning. Drawing from the Push–Pull Theory of Migration, the study affirms that rural poverty, unemployment, and limited amenities act as

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5.3 Recommendations

1. Enugu State Government should create a high powered security outfit to contend with the growing insecurity in the State resulting from rural urban influx.

2. Stiffer penalty should be put in place to control pollution, open defecation, and unnecessary bush burning.

3. The Government of Enugu State should build low housing on subsidized rent basis where the low income earners that migrated from the rural communities to the metropolis could settle.

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